

Evaluation of ICT Competency Skills of Librarians for Effective Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract:- The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the ICT Competency Skills of Librarians on the use of ICT for Effective Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The study was conceived against the background of the importance of ICT in library services and how librarians as information practitioners are being trained to effectively apply it in their service delivery. Five research objectives guided the study and five corresponding research questions were formulated to aid the research towards achieving its stated goals. The study employed survey research method. Considering the manageable size of the population; the entire population of 46 professional librarians in the academic libraries was used for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was titled: 'Competency Skills of Librarians in the ICT' for Effective Service Delivery Questionnaire (CSLICT) which was developed based on the research questions formulated for the study. The questionnaire was validated by three research experts from the Department of Library and Information Science in Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Waziri Umaru Federal Academic libraries, Birnin Kebbi and Kebbi State Academic libraries Dakingari respectively. The results of the findings was presented in tables and analyzed using frequency, percentage and the mean. Finding of the research work indicated that Librarians in academic libraries need to be competent in order to provide quality library and information services and that major competencies needed by these librarians to offer quality library services to users are public relations, communication, leadership and ICT skills. The study therefore recommended that, management of academic libraries should hasten up in the establishment of Internet services in their various libraries where available, such services should be scaled up. In-house training should be organized periodically to train both old and new staff to make them not only competent but also create awareness as new knowledge emerged in the field. Library management should endeavour to send as many librarians as possible to attend workshops, seminars, and conferences among others.

Keywords:- Competency Skills, Librarians, Service Delivery, Academic Library, Training, Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of the library in the information age and the place of ICT in an effective information provision and its wide acceptance in most academic libraries underscore the urgent need for training of librarians in ICT use. This is particularly true when viewed from the background that no matter how important a technology is, it is worthless or inactive without the human agent to apply and manipulate it. Librarians therefore, as managers of library resources stand conspicuously at the center of ICT application in libraries. The emergence of powerful technologies, vast amounts of information in multimedia and other digital formats and more technologically talented users means that librarians, particularly those in the academic libraries in Kebbi State are faced with the great challenge of dealing with information revolution [10]. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is unarguably man's foremost scientific invention and will remain so indefinitely. It has revolutionized every human activity with a far reaching impact on knowledge than Gutenberg's invention of the printing press in the 15th century, a development which liberalized literacy. [10] defined Information Technology (IT) as "the scientific, technological and engineering disciplines and the management technique used in information handling and processing; their applications; computers and their interactions with man and machines; and associated social economic and cultural matters". As a complementing resource perhaps, [19] views Communication Technology (CT) as "essentially encompassing all other technologies that enable humans to communicate and transmit information". Such will be the radio, television and telephone. He added that the integration of IT systems and CT systems develop into ICT system with enhanced capacities and capabilities for the transmission of information in multimedia formats.

Like all other professions, the influence of ICT pervades the library and information profession. Quite a lot of texts have been written on the impact, need for and the application of ICT in libraries, yet for the purpose of this study the role of ICT in effective library service delivery particularly academic libraries shall be re-emphasized. [4] recorded the benefits of ICT to library users. These include provision of speedy and easy access to information, provision of remote access to users, provision of round – the – clock access to users, access to unlimited information from different sources and providing

more current information. Indeed, ICT hold the key to effective and more appropriate library operations in this information age. Given the tremendous potentials of ICT applications in libraries, it will amount to a disaster both for librarians and library users if the former do not obtain the ICT skills relevant to the work. The most notable impact of the ICT in academic libraries is the internet. The internet is the new technological avenue to disseminate information to a larger and widely dispersed audience in a more speedy and accurate way. Internet helps to satisfy people's quest for knowledge and facilitates learning, teaching, research and publication, the objectives for which academic libraries are known, Afolabi [1]. Academic libraries are established to enhance the achievement of these objectives, through provision of bibliographic services to the academic community. No academic library worth its salt, therefore, can ignore the internet and remain relevant. This means that digital or virtual library resources must be organized for maximum exploitation by users, [18].

[7] noted that the introduction of internet is one of the greatest wizardry of the current ages. He defines it simply as "a global network of numerous computers and computer networks all over the world". It allows users to access information over the network. Information can also be exchanged, stored and retrieved. [7] listed the tools of the internet to include; electronic-mail (E-mail). File transfer protocol; telnet, use net news; and World Wide Web (www). [12] describe the new development as tools for information delivery in the new millennium. They enumerated the tools as follows: internet; www, e-mail, bibliographic control tools; online searching; creativity and innovations and the new information professionals. In the views of [4], ICT resources available for library include: personal computer; Compact Disk-Read-only-memory (CD-ROM); telefacsimile (fax); network; electro copying (scanning); and internet. [8] added that other ICT resources applicable in academic libraries could include; storage devices like optical and magnetic disks, printers, television, video recorder, taper recorder etc.

Academic libraries could apply varieties of telecommunication networks for different purposes; like the Local Area Network (LAN) to link the terminals within a library housekeeping system, Wide Area Network (WAN) to connect databases in remote systems, National data and voice networks to access videotext and telephone calls, and broadcast services to receive teletext [21].

These entire networks enhance interconnection and easy access to information. The main purpose of networking of academic libraries are to facilitate the exchange of bibliographic records, publication and distribution of electronic journals and other documents; making resources available in the databases to individual libraries and users; revealing the contents of a large number of libraries or a large number of publications using on-line public Access Catalogue (OPAC) interfaces, [12]. ICT resources can also be applied for housekeeping operation to enhance effective service delivery. Housekeeping operations here involves activities such as acquisition, cataloguing, circulation and charging functions, serials control, digitization of collections, security

of collections, etc. This application generally results in, improved operations; control of volume of activities efficiently and effectively, provision for new services and prevention of replications [2].

The task of ensuring a high degree of accessibility to library resources is that of the librarian. Librarians can be seen as a corps of professionals responsible for the collection of relevant materials and their organization, storage, retrieval, evaluation as well as dissemination of such materials to users. Librarians in tertiary institutions provide academic support to members of the university community, including students, researchers, lecturing staff, administrative members as well as others, [4].

This is by carrying out the aforementioned roles. These functions help the university to achieve its primary objectives of teaching, learning, research and consultancy services.

According to [20], information technologies are seen as enabling tools with a multiplier effect that can cut costs and improve the quality of delivery of basic infrastructure and services. Accordingly, ICTs includes the human resources that are needed to develop, install and operate the equipments and software as well as to set and enforce policy around their use. This is because with information communication technology things are made newer and easier for human beings and events can be coordinated without much stress and effect. The basic building block of Information Technologies industries is the skilled and semi-skilled manpower with basic skills for operating computers, using elementary functions of standard software. It includes the ability to make use of computer networks, in particular the internet; and to access the resources available through them. This underscores the need for ICT training among librarians. In addition, [20] added that electronic literacy is attractive to corporations (including libraries) because it promises better use of time, accelerated teaming, global reach, just pace and accountability. Furthermore, [19] noted that modern day librarians require specialized skills to navigate the ocean of information in order to address the specified information needs of their often sophisticated clientele system. He added further that the information resources in the cyberspace will continue to be more than those situated in any single library. Much of what is available in cyberspace is not relevant, reliable, and retainable for a long period. Here lies the relevance of librarians in the information age. According to [17] he would continue to explore, exploit and extend information available in all formats for the common good. Without adequate ICT skills it will be impossible to fulfill these roles.

Anunobi [4] infer the ICT competencies of librarians in Nigerian tertiary institutions, including those in Kebbi State, Nigeria zone, by the application of ICT facilities in libraries' administrative purposes. Other areas of application according to her are cataloguing and classification as well as in acquisition. The Wikipedia free dictionary defines training as "the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies". Training has specific goals of improving one's capability, capacity and performance. It forms the core of apprenticeships and provides the backbone of content at institutes of

technology. In addition to the basic training required for a trade, occupation or profession, observers of the labour market recognize the need to continue training beyond initial qualifications; to maintain, upgrade and update skills throughout working life. People within many professions and occupations may refer to this sort of training as professional development.[16]. [23] identified different types of training but Job Training and Development is more relevant to this discussion. Some commentators use a similar term for workplace learning to improve performance. [9]. Training and Development examples of services beyond those offered by employers are; career counseling, skill assessment, and supportive services. One can generally categorize such training as on-the-job or off-the-job.

On-the-job training takes place in a normal working situation, using the actual tools, equipments, documents or materials that trainees will use when fully trained. On-the-job training has a general reputation as most effective for vocational work.

Off-the-job training takes place away from normal work situations, implying that the employee does not count as a directly productive worker while such training lasts. Off-the-job training has the advantage that it allows people to get away from work and concentrate more thoroughly on the training itself.

For the purpose of this study, training shall be seen as the processes engaged in to acquire ICT competencies by librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Varieties of methods could be employed in ICT training. [6] listed 5 methods of acquiring ICT skills to include teaching through friends, self-teaching; reading books/manuals; training in cyber cafes, and lectures in faculties. Other training methods could include: training on-the-job; training in the university's ICT centre; in-house training and through seminars and workshops. Some training methods are more effective than others. Effectiveness of training is the ultimate objective for any method. The methods employed, therefore, by librarians in the academic libraries in Kebbi State to obtain ICT skills is the preoccupation of this study as it appears that most of them are left on their own to pursue these skills. Records shows that a good number of workers, including librarians are not eager to expend personal resources for self development except when it has direct bearing on promotion. The result at best is half-baked, incompetent and betwixt personnel.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Information and Communication Technology has unstoppably revolutionized every sphere of human endeavour including of course the library. Indeed, the library appears to be its primary constituency as the technology is purely information. The global practice in library and information management is fast moving into the electronic platform. Academic libraries, particularly in the north west of Nigeria increasingly face the danger of becoming obsolete and irrelevant if they remain in the purely conventional terrain, hence the digitization efforts. However this paradigm shift has

necessitated that individual librarians adjust accordingly by obtaining relevant ICT competencies. This is the only way they can initiate the migration and sustenance of their resources in a networked environment, as well as remain relevant themselves.

The need for librarians to obtain ICT skills is particularly compelling in view of their role as the inter-phase between information resources and users. This is more so that operational activities in computerized libraries are becoming increasingly sophisticated, as new technologies are displayed to offer users the options to search for required information online or through internet access. Most users seeking information are unskilled in the use of ICT facilities and therefore depend on the librarian's expertise in accessing the information. It will be a disaster therefore, if librarians are incapable of meeting this noble obligation. Librarians require skills in areas such as computer use, accessing online databases, downloading files from online databases, creating own databases, communicating using e-mail and voice mail, use of search engines, digitization of documents, etc. These skills can be acquired through varieties of methods such as self-teaching, teaching by friends, in-house training, training in commercial centers etc. The acquisition of ICT skills by librarians calls for a well organized and properly articulated planning as opposed to a haphazard method. This is because the training method employed to obtain ICT skills has direct implications on the output, as learning outcome is greatly influenced by the learning method. It is the ICT training methods employed by librarians in Academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria and their implications on information services delivery that this study seek to establish.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the ICT competency skills and training methods of librarians for effective service delivery in academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Specifically, it is aimed at:

- Identifying the ICT skills required for training librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria.
- Determine the ICT skills possessed by Librarians in academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria.
- Established the means by librarians can acquire these needed ICT competency Skills
- Identifying the constraints associated with the acquisition of these needed ICT competencies.
- Proffer strategies to be employed to meet these constraints of acquiring the needed ICT competencies in the academic libraries in Kebbi state.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

This study sets to answer the following questions.

- What are the essential ICT competencies Skills required for training librarians in the academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria?
- Which of these competencies do these librarians possess?
- By what means can these librarians acquire these needed ICT competency skills?

- What constraints are associated with the acquisition of these needed ICT competency skills?
- What strategies can be employed to meet these constraints of acquiring the needed ICT competency Skills?

V. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study, which examines the ICT competencies required of the librarians of the academic libraries in Kebbi State, will hopefully be of great benefit to the Institution's library managers, librarians working in libraries sectors and their patrons in the following ways:

It will enable the management of relevant regulatory body appreciate the need for the provision of necessary Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities to various institutions and organize constant training for Librarians to be in tune with the changing face of librarianship.

It will help the library management to identify existing gaps in their librarians' ICT competencies and organizing training to fill such gaps. It will also help library management to develop relevant training programmes generally for staff that will make them more skillful in the provision of quality services to their users.

It will assist library managers in the various institutions under review o in the recruitment of new staff based on the identified gaps in requisite ICT competencies in clarifying common goals for all employees. It will enable aspiring librarians to become familiar with the core ICT competencies needed in their respective libraries and this will help them make effort for the acquisition of these competencies by sponsoring themselves for training even when the institution refuses to do so. The library patrons will develop more confidence in academic Librarians capability to cope with the challenges of the 21st Century information services provision and become attracted to make better use of library services with the hope that they will receive better guidance from the librarians.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey research design. [11] highlighted the characteristics of descriptive survey research as having a pre-established instrument most likely developed by the researcher, most responses to the questions on the survey are quantitative or will be summarized in a quantitative way and the sample is selected from a larger population or group to allow the study's finding to be generalized back to the group. All the features highlighted above are in tandem with this study and therefore will be suitable to it.

B. Area of Study

"The study was conducted in Kebbi State which is in the North West Geo political zone of Nigeria. The state was created out from part of Sokoto State in 1991 and it is bordered by Sokoto State, Niger State, Zamfara State, Dosso Region in the Republic of Niger and the nation of Benin. Kebbi state has

its capital located at Birnin Kebbi. It has a total area of 36,800 km² (14,200 sq mi). Kebbi State consists of 21 Local Government Areas (LGAs), four emirate councils (Gwandu, Argungu, Yauri and Zuru), and 35 districts. And it has a total population of 4,440,050 as at 2016 population census. The choice of Kebbi State for this study is because it houses a quite number of functional academic libraries [14]."

C. Population of the Study

"The population of this study consisted of all academic librarians and Senior Library Officers in seven (7) tertiary institutions in Kebbi State including Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Waziri Umaru Federal Academic libraries, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State Academic libraries, Dakingari, Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi and School of Health Technology, Jega respectively. The distribution is shown in Table 1 below:"

S/N	Name of Institution	Respondents
1	Federal University Birnin Kebbi (FUBK)	12
2	Kebbi State University of Science and Technology (KUSUSTA)	10
3	Waziri Umaru Federal Academic libraries, Birnin Kebbi (WUFEDPOLY)	10
4	Kebbi State Academic libraries, Dakingari (KESPODAK)	6
5	Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu.	6
6	School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi	1
7	School of Health Technology, Jega	1
Total		46

Source: Offices of: The librarians, nominal role (2022).

D. Sample and Sampling Technique

The entire population of 46 representing 100% was used for the study. This is on the account of the small number of the population. Consequently, there was no application of any sampling technique. According to [15], when the population of a study is small, all the population should be used.

E. Instrument for Data Collection

The researcher employed the use of a structured questionnaire for data collection. The instrument was carefully structured by the researchers based on the research questions formulated to guide the study. The questionnaire comprised of both structured and unstructured questions. The unstructured set of questions was meant to provide wider opportunity for respondents to express themselves. The questionnaire was titled: 'Competency Skills of Librarian on Information and Communication' (CSLICT).

F. Validation of the Instrument

To ensure the face validity of the instrument, the researchers presented the questionnaire to three lecturers in the Department of Library and Information Science, who were versed in research. They were requested to critically examine

the sets of questions to determine their suitability to the phenomenon being investigated. Following the validation, all adjustments made to the instrument were incorporated into the final copy of the instrument.

G. Method of Data Collection

The Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents by the researchers through personal contact and with the help of two trained research assistants. The assistants were chosen from among the population for purpose of familiarity with the research environments. They were instructed to administer the questionnaires to only professional librarians to the exclusion of non-professionals, and to follow up for reminder and collection of completed questionnaires.

H. Method of Data Analysis

The data obtained through the questionnaire was presented in tables and analyzed using frequency, simple percentage and the mean. Sections that sought to determine the applicability of items was analyzed using simple percentage,

while section that was designed to verify the effectiveness of training methods and opinions of respondents on given phenomena was analyzed by the mean. Similarly, any item that scored the average of 50 percent and above will be accepted while those below the average score will be rejected. Likewise, for the means 2.50 indicate acceptance while any score below 2.50 indicate rejections.

VII. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

A total of forty-six (46) questionnaires were distributed and all the copies were filled and returned by the respondents representing 100% response rate. They were organized and analyzed by means of mean (\bar{X}) and percentages (%) and presented in tables. The tables below show that the total frequency of respondents is forty-six (46) with a criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 1: What are the essential ICT competencies Skills required for training librarians in the academic libraries in Kebbi State, Nigeria?

S/N	Competencies	SA	A	DA	SD	Mean
I	Forecasting the future and proffering appropriate solution	5	8	23	10	2.17
Ii	Role assignment to staff	28	10	3	5	3.33
Iii	Development of team spirit	36	5	1	4	3.57
Iv	Appreciate change and develop continuous professional skills	34	5	2	5	3.48
V	Management of Finances	25	11	6	4	3.24
Vi	Policy making skills	29	7	3	7	3.26
Vii	Organizing skills	37	5	2	2	3.67
Viii	On-line searching	35	5	3	3	3.57
Ix	Word processing	15	26	2	3	3.15
X	Providing virtual information	22	14	6	4	3.17
Xi	Creating databases	37	7	2	0	3.76
Xii	Strongbusiness communication	33	7	3	3	3.52
Xiii	Interpersonal communication	35	7	3	1	3.65
Xiv	Patience and listening ability	32	9	2	3	3.52
Xv	Relating cordially with others	40	5	1	0	3.85
Xvi	Sympathetic	38	3	4	1	3.70
Xvii	Research skills	36	3	4	3	3.57

This table reveals that role assignment to staff, development of team spirit, appreciating change and developing continuing professional education skills, good management of finance, policy making competencies, organizing on-line searching, word processing, providing virtual information, creating data bases, strong business communication, interpersonal communication practice and listening, relating cordially with others, sympathetic and research competencies are all needed for effective provision of quality services. However, forecasting the future and proffering appropriate solution had a negative perception from the respondents. It had a below average mean of 2.17.

Research Question 2: Which of these competencies do the librarians possess?

S/N	Competencies	SA	A	DA	SD	Mean
I	Forecasting the future	15	3	20	8	2.54
Ii	Role assignment to staff	11	5	18	12	2.32
Iii	Development of team sprit	27	12	4	3	3.37
Iv	Good management of finance	8	3	30	5	2.30
V	Good policy making skills	7	1	28	10	2.11
Vi	Organizing skills	17	3	10	16	2.46
vii	On-line searching skills	4	5	5	32	1.59
viii	Word processing	4	3	9	30	1.59
ix	Providing virtual information	5	6	9	26	1.78
X	Creating databases	2	5	8	31	1.52
xi	Strong business communication	8	17	11	10	2.50
xii	Interpersonal communication	29	9	3	5	3.35
xiii	Patience and listening ability	20	5	15	6	2.85
xiv	Relating cordially with others	20	14	9	3	3.11
xv	Sympathetic	12	17	14	3	2.83
xvi	Research skills	13	15	12	6	2.76

The above table depicts that of all the needed competencies the highest possessed by the respondents is development of team spirit with the highest mean of 3.37. Interpersonal communication and relating cordially with others follows with a mean score of 3.24 and 3.11. The fourth in the rank is patient and listening ability with 2.85. The others are sympathetic 2.83, research skills 2.76, forecasting the future 2.54 and strong business communication, 2.50 respectively. However, the other competencies skills were rated below 2.50 bench mark including organizing skills with mean score of 2.46, role assignment to staff with 2.32 mean score, good management of finances 2.30 and policy-making skills 2.11. Similarly, it was revealed that providing virtual information, On-line searching, word processing, and creating databases of has a mean scores of 1.78 1.59, 1.59 and 1.52 respectively which is also below the acceptable bench mark of 2.50.

Research Question 3:

By what means can these Librarians acquired these needed competencies?

S/N	Methods of Competencies Acquisition	No. of Responses	%
i	Workshops/Conferences/Symposia	24	52.17
ii	Induction/Orientation	32	69.57
iii	Participatory Management training	35	76.09
iv	On-the-job training	28	60.87
v	Formal professional education	46	100
vi	Seminar	41	89.13
vii	Job Rotation	29	63.04
viii	Internship	36	78.26

From the result on method of training by which the respondents acquired their skills, it shows that 24 academic

Librarians representing 52.17% have ever attended workshops / conference / symposia; 32 respondents representing 69.57% agreed to have attended induction and orientation; 35 representing 76.07% accepted partaking in participatory management training; 28 respondents representing 60.87% said that they acquired their skills through on-the-job training; 46 respondents representing 100% agreed to have acquired their skills through professional library education; while 29 representing 63.04% of the respondents stated that they acquired their skills through job rotation. 36 of the respondents representing 78.26% agreed to have acquired their skills through internship. This result indicated that all the stated ways of through which librarians can acquire skills as proposed by this research are accepted with each scoring above 50%.

Research Question 4: What constraints are associated with the acquisition of these needed competencies?

To elicit the information from the Librarians in the academic Libraries in Kebbi State Nigeria on the constraints associated with the acquisition of these needed ICT competencies the criterion mean of 2.50 was used as cut-off point in deciding their challenge. The analysis of the data is presented in table 7 below.

Table 5: Mean responses of Librarians in the academic Libraries in Kebbi State Nigeria on the challenges confronting them in the acquisition of needed competencies.

S/N	challenges confronting Librarians	SA	A	DA	SD	Mean
i	Lack of Budgeting provision for training	28	11	3	4	3.37
ii	Lack of Time	2	2	6	36	1.35
iii	Limited Opportunities for relevant training	33	7	3	3	3.52
iv	Lack of training facilities	17	19	5	5	3.04
v	Lack of training officer in Librarianship field to handle training	16	21	4	5	3.04
vi	Lack of policy on training	4	5	3	34	1.54

The analysis shown on the above table on challenges impeding the acquisition of skills indicates that limited opportunities for relevant training with 3.52 rank highest among the challenges faced by the respondents. This is followed by lack of budgetary provision for training with 3.37. Lack of training officer as well as lack of training facilities ranked third with 3.04 each. Others are policy on training with 1.54 and lack of lack of time as the least and last with 1.35.

Research question 5: How can these Challenges be overcome?

Table 6: percentage responses of strategies for overcoming the challenges of acquisition of ICT competencies skills.

S/N	Strategies for overcoming the Challenges	No. of Responses	Percentages
i	Provision of fund through budgetary allocation for staff training	46	100
ii	Staff should be give opportunity to attend conferences, workshops and seminars	43	93.48
iii	Provision of necessary facilities for practice	40	86.96

In answering these questions all the respondents suggested that budgetary provision should be made by the management for Continuing Education of Librarians, and that the management of the institution should at least be releasing not less than three (3) Librarians to attend conferences, seminars and workshop anytime such professional workshops, conferences and seminars are organized. 40 respondents out of 46 representing 86.96% said training facilities should be provided in the academic libraries for librarians.

VIII. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the study revealed that all but one of the essential ICT competencies are needed by the librarians to provide quality services to their users. The ranking shows that relating cordially with others and been sympathetic which are traits of public relations as listed by [11] ranked highest. The only item perceived as not necessary competency required for effective provision of library services is forecasting the future, and proffering appropriate solution. The reason for this perception may be because not all the librarians are sectional heads or heads of their libraries. They must have wrongly assumed that the role of forecasting and proffering appropriate solution rest with only the heads. Their perception agrees with [5] who linked this to a leader when he said a competent leader must be flexible and have the capability to plan within the limited resources and be able to forecast the future and proffer appropriate solution to achieve organizational goals.

The findings of this study show that from the list of competencies accepted to be required by the librarians; the librarians of the academic libraries in the areas under study do not possess all the ICT competencies. These ICT competencies possessed by these librarians are the pre-21st century competencies that every librarian of that era is expected to have. Competencies such as forecasting the

future, good policy making, organizing, on-line searching, word processing, creating databases and providing virtual information which are the characteristics of 21st century librarianship are nearly non existence. This result of this study in this respect differs from [11] who asserted that librarians of today and tomorrow must possess ICT competencies if they must remain relevant in the present form of librarianship.

The findings are also contrary to [19] who stated that 21st library services is predicted on the evolving electronic environment and that professionals librarians require competencies in information management to meet the demands of the new information environment – migrating to web. The findings however agrees with [9] findings of lack of Information and Communication Technology competencies amongst the librarians of research libraries as the bane for poor library services provision to users.

The result of the study further revealed that only few librarians attend workshops and seminars. This result is contrary to [18] view that for any librarian to be in line with the scheme of the changing face of librarianship, necessary skills must be acquired through sponsored major conferences, workshops and tutorials. The result also implies that ICT competencies acquired were through induction / orientation, formal / professional education, internship, on-the-job training and seldomly through participatory management training and job rotation. Although these methods of competencies acquisition agrees with [6], adequate competencies may not be acquired if the status quo of the academic Libraries and the library schools are still traditional.

The finding of this study also reveal that lack of budgetary provision for training, limited opportunities for relevant training, lack of training facilities and lack of training officers in librarianship field to handle training are the

challenges that confront the librarians in the acquisition of needed competencies for the provision of the quality services to users. This result agrees with [16] who stated that one of the challenges for the acquisition of competencies is lack of appropriate working environment. It also agrees with [20] who hinged the challenges of competencies acquisition on lack of funds, which could be linked to non-provision of budgetary allocation for training. Other challenges like the limited opportunities for relevant training and lack of training officers conforms with [11] summary of the challenges for the competencies acquisitions. However the results of this study disagree with [11] lack of time on the part of the librarians as a challenge. This is because the respondents totally disagreed with the lack of time as a challenge. Lack of policy on training was also not accepted to be a challenge for the acquisition of competency. The reason for non-acceptance of this as a challenge may be because policy statements and their interpretation is dependent on the management of the libraries and the Academics in general.

As a measure to overcoming these challenges, the result reveals that most of the respondents stated that management of academics should make adequate funds available through budgetary provision to allow more librarians to attend training that will improve and make them grow in line with developments in librarianship as it unfolds. The respondents emphasizes funding because other challenges such as lack of training facilities and lack of enough competent hands to train other librarians rest on adequate funding. If enough funds are provided, more people will be trained thereby increasing the number of resource persons to be handling further training. The challenge of limited opportunities for relevant training also rests on funding.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Academic libraries library management should hasten the establishment of Internet services in their various libraries.
- Organising in-house training should be instituted to periodically train both old and new staff to make them not only competent but also create awareness as new knowledge emerges in the field.
- Library management should endeavour to send as many librarians as possible to attend workshops, seminars, and conferences.
- Librarians on their own should sacrifice their hard earned salaries to attend seminars, conferences and workshops. This is very necessary because their productivity is hinged on their level of competencies.
- The Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) course unit should be more of practical than the theory. The present training where students do not have access to computers throughout course of studies in library schools should be discouraged.
- Academic libraries librarians must also strive to re-tool themselves by continually updating their knowledge after their studies in library schools in order to continue to fit in the emerging electronic information environment.

X. CONCLUSION

Librarians will be able to acquire the necessary competencies if adequate fund are made available and librarians released to re-tool themselves in order to properly provide enhanced services for users in the evolving electronic information environment, which is the characteristics of 21st century librarianship. Most of the libraries in these institutions lack necessarily equipment like computers, and Internet facilities, which are the major characteristics of 21st century libraries. And because these facilities are not available on-the-job training is limited to traditional librarianship. Only few librarians have adequate knowledge of the 21st century librarianship and thus making training officers scarce and Majority of the librarians in the Academic libraries do not possess the sufficient ICT competencies skills.

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